

Cupisnique Culture Religion

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Entry tags: Pre-Inka Religions, Andes, Peru, Religious Group, South American Religions

The Cupisnique culture developed along the North Coast of Peru (between the Lambayeque and the Nepeña valleys) during the Initial Period and the Early Horizon (ca. 1600-400 BCE). During this time frame, several ceremonial complexes composed of plazas surrounded by mounds were built in the Northern Peruvian valleys. While monumental complexes were also built in other parts of the Central Andean region during this period (i.e., Central Coast of Peru, Peruvian Central and Northern Highlands), the Northern Peruvian valleys were marked by the presence of specific architectural features (e.g., colonnades and wide stairways), and the use of black pottery produced in a range of styles. Research on the Cupisnique culture has been conducted since the 1940s (Larco 1945). Due to iconographic similarities with Chavín de Huántar, Cupisnique has been either labeled as a cultural expression that preceded and heavily influenced the emergence of the Early Horizon's Chavín cult (Larco 1945) or a coastal version of Chavín (Tello 1943). Recent research (Burger and Salazar 2008) suggests that Cupisnique was a local development and that, along with other coastal, highland, and Amazonian sources, inspired Chavín cult and iconography. Jason Nesbitt (2012) also argued that the Cupisnique culture can be subdivided into two interacting sociopolitical units ("social fields") that shared the same religious ideology. The Northern Cupisnique social field included the Lambayeque, Zaña, and Jequetepeque valleys, while the Southern Cupisnique social fields comprised the area between the Chicama and Nepeña valleys. Excavations conducted at ceremonial centers and coastal villages help us shed light on the religious practices of the people that occupied the North Coast of Peru during the Initial Period and the Early Horizon.

Date Range: 1600 BCE - 400 BCE

Region: Cupisnique Culture Religion

Region tags: Peru, Andes

Area occupied by the Cupisnique culture

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

— Yes

Notes: Pottery featuring Cupisnique-like traits (i.e., shape and decorations) was found in the Northern Peruvian Highlands (Cajamarca area) and in the Central Peruvian Highlands. While it is still unclear if these pots were produced in the Peruvian North Coast and subsequently traded or were made by highland potters imitating North Coast artifacts, they suggest that the Cupisnique people were part of a pan-regional interaction network.

Reference: Burger, Richard L. "Understanding the Socioeconomic Trajectory of Chavín De Huántar: A New Radiocarbon Sequence and Its Wider Implications". *Latin American Antiquity* 30, no. 2 (2019): 373-92. <https://doi.org/10.1017/laq.2019.17>.

Reference: Burger, Richard L.. *Chavin and the Origins of Andean Civilization*. Thames and Hudson, 1992.

Reference: Matsumoto, Yuichi, and Jason Nesbitt. "¿cupisnique En La Sierra Central? Piezas De "cupisnique Clásico" En Piquimina Y Campanayuc Rumi". *YACHAQ* 4, no. 2 (2021): 71-95. <https://doi.org/10.46363/yachaq.v4i2.168>.

Reference: Burtenshaw-Zumstein, Julia T.. "Cupisnique, Tembladera, Chongoyape, Chavín? A Typology of Ceramic Styles from Formative Period Northern Peru, 1800-200 BC". Doctoral Thesis, University of East Anglia, 2014. <https://ueaeprints.uea.ac.uk/id/eprint/54452/>.

Reference: Onuki, Yoshio. "Cupisnique En La Sierra De Cajamarca". *Arqueológicas* 25 (n.d.): 67-81.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religion have official political support

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Notes: This Large religious groups also interacted with other Large religious groups located in the Northern and Central Peruvian Highlands, and in the southernmost part of the Northern Peruvian Coast (Casma Valley). Prieto argued that small fishing communities like Gramalote in the Moche Valley may have had local religious practices, but may have also participated in rituals carried out at regional-scale monumental centers.

Reference: Quilter, Jeffrey. *The Ancient Central Andes*. 2nd ed.. Routledge, 2022.

Reference: Burger, Richard L.. *Chavin and the Origins of Andean Civilization*. Thames and Hudson, 1992.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel. "The Social Dynamics and Economic Interactions of the Households at Gramalote, a Small-scale Residential Settlement During the Second Millennium BC on the North Coast of Peru". *Latin American Antiquity* 29, no. 3 (September 2018): 532–51. <https://doi.org/10.1017/laq.2018.10>.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Even though there is no striking evidence, ceremonies may have been conducted by priests/shamans that may have performed rituals under the effect of hallucinogens. Burials of possible shamans have been found in the coastal village of Gramalote by Gabriel Prieto.

Reference: Burger, Richard L.. *Chavin and the Origins of Andean Civilization*. Thames and Hudson, 1992.

Reference: Park Huntington, Yumi . "Emblems of Cultural Identity in Early Andean Art: Engraved Head Motifs on Cupisnique Ceramics". In *Ceramics of Ancient America: Multidisciplinary Approaches*, edited by Yumi Park Huntington, Dean E. Arnold, and Johanna Minich, 131–55. Gainesville, FL: University Press of Florida, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.5744/florida/9780813056067.003.0005>.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel. "The Social Dynamics and Economic Interactions of the Households at Gramalote, a Small-scale Residential Settlement During the Second Millennium BC on the North Coast of Peru". *Latin American Antiquity* 29, no. 3 (September 2018): 532–51. <https://doi.org/10.1017/laq.2018.10>.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel. "The Temple of the Fishermen: Early Ceremonial Architecture at Gramalote, a Residential Settlement of the Second Millennium B.C., North Coast of Peru". *Journal of Field*

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Cupisnique ceremonial centers are marked by the presence of stepped mounds usually build using conical adobe bricks. These mounds are not isolated, but rather part of large complexes that include several buildings. The buildings are usually organized around squared, rectangular or circular plazas, forming a U-like shape. Ceremonial mounds often featured wide staircases and colonnades leading to sunken plazas and rooms located atop of the building. Coastal villages like Gramalote in the Moche Valley featured smaller ceremonial buildings, such as a sunken squared plaza with a central hearth.

Reference: Burger, Richard L.. *Chavin and the Origins of Andean Civilization*. Thames and Hudson, 1992.

Reference: Moore, Jerry D.. *Cultural Landscapes in the Ancient Andes: Archaeologies of Place*. University Press of Florida, 2005.

Reference: Zoubek, Thomas A.. “The Initial Period Occupation of Huaca El Gallo/huaca La Gallina, Virú Valley, Peru and Its Implications for Guañape Phase Social Complexity”. PhD Dissertation, Yale University, 1997.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel. “The Social Dynamics and Economic Interactions of the Households at Gramalote, a Small-scale Residential Settlement During the Second Millennium BC on the North Coast of Peru”. *Latin American Antiquity* 29, no. 3 (September 2018): 532–51. <https://doi.org/10.1017/laq.2018.10>.

Reference: Shimada, Izumi. “The Batan Grande-la Leche Archaeological Project: The First Two Seasons”. *Journal of Field Archaeology* 8, no. 4 (1981): 405–46. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/529792>.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel. “The Temple of the Fishermen: Early Ceremonial Architecture at Gramalote, a Residential Settlement of the Second Millennium B.C., North Coast of Peru”. *Journal of Field Archaeology* 43, no. 3 (2018): 200–221. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00934690.2018.1441573>.

In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 12000

Notes: Huaca Herederos Grande at the Caballo Muerto Complex in the Moche Valley (120x100m)

Reference: Moore, Jerry D.. Cultural Landscapes in the Ancient Andes: Archaeologies of Place. University Press of Florida, 2005.

Reference: Alva, Walter L. . "Investigaciones En El Complejo Formativo Con Arquitectura Monumental De Purulen, Costa Norte Del Peru: Informe Preliminar". In Beitrage Zur Allgemeinen Und Vergleichenden Archaologie, 8:283-300. Mainz am Rhein: Philipp von Zabern, 1986.

Reference: Burger, Richard L.. Chavin and the Origins of Andean Civilization. Thames and Hudson, 1992.

Reference: Nesbitt, Jason. "Excavations at Caballo Muerto: An Investigation into the Origins of the Cupisnique Culture". PhD dissertation, Yale University, 2012.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 21

Notes: Huaca Cortada at the Caballo Muerto Complex in the Moche Valley.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Possible ancestral tombs ("collar tombs") were identified by Thomas Zoubek in the Huacapongo Valley and Amedeo Sghinolfi in the Carabamba Valley. These tombs were composed of a circular stone structure (diameters ranging between 30 cm and 2 m) surrounding the deceased, who was buried in a pit dug in the ground and accompanied by few grave goods (shells, beads, animal bones, bone objects, potsherds). These collar tombs

included both infants and adults that were placed either in a flexed or in an extended position. In the Huacapongo Valley, these tombs were located near large ceremonial centers (Huaca El Gallo and Huaca La Gallina), while in the Carabamba Valley they were at the bottom of a quebrada. These burials may have reaffirmed linkages between the communities that inhabited these Northern Peruvian Valleys and their land.

Reference: Zoubek, Thomas A. "Archaeological Evidence of Preceramic/Initial Period Ancestor Worship and Its Relevance to Early Andean Coastal Social Formations". *Journal of the Steward Anthropological Society* 26, no. 1-2 (1998): 71-112.

Reference: Sghinolfi, Amedeo. *Life in Between: Prehispanic Settlement Patterns of the Carabamba Valley, Northern Peru*. London, Ontario: Western University, 2021. <https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/etd/8318/>.

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: Several Cupisnique cemeteries were identified by Larco Hoyle in the Chicama Valley and Carlos Elera in the Lambayeque Valley. Elera's research at Puemape show that Cupisnique funerary patterns display a high degree of continuity over time (shallow pits, bodies in a flexed position and wrapped in cloths/mats, few offerings like gourds, pots, shells, animal bone tools, anthracite mirrors, necklaces, pigments).

Reference: Elera Arevalo, Carlos Gustavo. "La Cultura Cupisnique a Partir De Los Datos Arqueológicos De Puémape". In *De Cupisnique a Los Incas. El Arte Del Valle De Jequetepeque*, edited by Luis Jaime Castillo and Cecilia Pardo, 68-111. Lima, Peru: Museo de Arte de Lima - MALI, 2009.

Reference: Elera Arevalo, Carlos Gustavo. "The Puemape Site and the Cupisnique Culture: A Case Study on the Origins and Development of Complex Society in the Central Andes, Peru". Doctoral thesis, University of Calgary, 1998. <http://hdl.handle.net/1880/26224>.

Reference: Larco Hoyle, Rafael. *Los Cupisniques*, 1945.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel. "The Social Dynamics and Economic Interactions of the Households at Gramalote, a Small-scale Residential Settlement During the Second Millennium BC on the North Coast of Peru". *Latin American Antiquity* 29, no. 3 (September 2018): 532-51. <https://doi.org/10.1017/laq.2018.10>.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned in the previous sections, Cupisnique ceremonial centers are marked by the presence of stepped mounds usually build using conical adobe bricks. These mounds are not isolated, but rather part of large complexes that include several buildings. The buildings are usually organized around squared, rectangular or circular plazas, forming a U-like shape. Ceremonial mounds often featured wide staircases and colonnades leading to sunken plazas and rooms located atop of the building. Coastal villages like Gramalote in the Moche Valley featured smaller ceremonial buildings, such as a sunken squared plaza with a central hearth.

↳ Altars:

– No

Devotional markers:

– Yes

Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: Most Cupisnique ceremonial centers featured rectangular sunken plazas located next/in front of ceremonial platforms. Such plazas were likely used for large gatherings involving members of small communities that contributed to the construction of such centers. In some cases (e.g., Huaca de los Reyes in the caballo Muerto Complex in the Moche Valley), there were also small rectangular plazas that may have been used for more "exclusive" rituals that involved only a specific group of people (perhaps a religious elite).

Reference: Nesbitt, Jason. "Excavations at Caballo Muerto: An Investigation into the Origins of the Cupisnique Culture". PhD dissertation, Yale University, 2012.

Reference: Burger, Richard L. Chavin and the Origins of Andean Civilization. Thames and Hudson, 1992.

Reference: Moore, Jerry D. Cultural Landscapes in the Ancient Andes: Archaeologies of Place. University Press of Florida, 2005.

Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Some public spaces

Notes: Iconography can be found at the Cupisnique ceremonial centers (polychrome clay friezes - painted in yellow, red, blue, black), but also on portable objects, especially incised motifs on black polished stirrup-spout bottles. The adherents to this religion depicted a variety of motifs, including felines, spiders, snakes, anthropomorphic figures with feline traits, fangs, wings, or depicted as decapitators.

Reference: Burger, Richard L. Chavin and the Origins of Andean Civilization. Thames and Hudson, 1992.

Reference: Alva Meneses, Ignacio. "Los Complejos De Cerro Ventarrón Y Collud-zarpán: Del Precerámico Al Formativo En El Valle De Lambayeque". Boletín De Arqueología PUCP 12 (2008): 97-117. <https://doi.org/10.18800/boletindearqueologiapucp.200801.005>.

Reference: Salazar Burger, Lucy, and Richard L. Burger. "La Araña En La Iconografía Del Horizonte Temprano En La Costa Norte Del Perú". In *Beiträge Zur Allgemeinen Und Vergleichenden Archäologie*, Vol. 4, 1982.

Reference: Shibata, Koichiro. "Cosmología Tripartita En Huaca Partida, Valle Bajo De Nepeña". *Indiana* 34, no. 1 (2017): 13-29. <https://doi.org/10.18441/ind.v34i1.13-29>.

Reference: Nesbitt, Jason. "Excavations at Caballo Muerto: An Investigation into the Origins of the Cupisnique Culture". PhD dissertation, Yale University, 2012.

Reference: Cordy-Collins, Alana. "Archaism or Tradition?: The Decapitation Theme in Cupisnique and Moche Iconography". *Latin American Antiquity* 3, no. 3 (September 1992): 206-20. <https://doi.org/10.2307/971715>.

Reference: Franco Jordán, Régulo, and Feren Castillo Luján. "Hallazgo De Una Pintura Mural Temprana En La Huaca Tomabal, Valle De Virú, Perú". *Arqueología Y Sociedad* 37 (2022): 7-25. <https://doi.org/10.15381/arqueolsoc.2022n37.e23165>.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

Notes: These eyes (depicted on anthropomorphic figures) usually feature eccentric pupils. This trait also appear in the later/coeval Chavin art.

Reference: Burger, Richard L.. *Chavin and the Origins of Andean Civilization*. Thames and Hudson, 1992.

Reference: Park Huntington, Yumi . "Emblems of Cultural Identity in Early Andean Art: Engraved Head Motifs on Cupisnique Ceramics". In *Ceramics of Ancient America: Multidisciplinary Approaches*, edited by Yumi Park Huntington, Dean E. Arnold, and Johanna Minich, 131-55. Gainesville, FL: University Press of Florida, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.5744/florida/9780813056067.003.0005>.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Snakes, spiders, and felines may have been considered supernatural beings and were depicted on both ceremonial centers and portable objects. These animals may have been connected to water and fertility.

Reference: Salazar Burger, Lucy, and Richard L. Burger. "La Araña En La Iconografía Del Horizonte Temprano En La Costa Norte Del Perú". In *Beiträge Zur Allgemeinen Und Vergleichenden Archäologie*, Vol. 4, 1982.

Reference: Burger, Richard L.. *Chavin and the Origins of Andean Civilization*. Thames and Hudson, 1992.

Reference: Alva Meneses, Ignacio. "Los Complejos De Cerro Ventarrón Y Collud-zarpán:

Del Precerámico Al Formativo En El Valle De Lambayeque”. *Boletín De Arqueología PUCP* 12 (2008): 97-117. <https://doi.org/10.18800/boletindearqueologiapucp.200801.005>.

Reference: Burtenshaw-Zumstein, Julia T.. “Cupisnique, Tembladera, Chongoyape, Chavín? A Typology of Ceramic Styles from Formative Period Northern Peru, 1800-200 BC”. Doctoral Thesis, University of East Anglia, 2014.
<https://ueaeprints.uea.ac.uk/id/eprint/54452/>.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Anthropomorphic beings depicted on ceremonial centers may represent supernatural beings. In some cases, These beings feature animal traits, such as fangs, snakes hanging from body parts, wings. For example, large (ca. 2 m tall) clay heads with fangs were found at Huaca de los Reyes (Caballo Muerto Complex in the Moche Valley) and Thomas Pozorski interpreted them as the depiction of a possible creator deity. At the same site, bipedal anthropomorphic figures were interpreted as culture hero/es, while smaller anthropomorphic profile heads may have represented aides linked to this culture hero/es. More recently, Yumi Huntington interpreted these smaller heads, which feature animal traits, as possible shamans/religious leaders that were able to travel through the sky (when depicted with bird feathers), earth (jaguar fangs), and the underworld (caiman teeth). Similar anthropomorphic figures were found at Cerro Blanco in the Nepeña Valley on different levels of a stepped platform. On the highest level, a raptorial bird (upper world) was depicted and below it was a winged anthropomorphic figure. The latter was perhaps a mediator between the upper world and the Earth, represented by a feline/anthropomorphic feline depicted on a third level. A variety of possible supernatural anthropomorphic figures were also represented on pottery. In particular, individuals with a mix of human and animal (spider, fish, bird) traits were depicted while decapitating/holding human heads. Anthropomorphic figures with snake/jaguar-like and warrior traits were also depicted on rock art, more specifically on geoglyphs found in the lower Carabamba Valley.

Reference: Burtenshaw-Zumstein, Julia T.. “Cupisnique, Tembladera, Chongoyape, Chavín? A Typology of Ceramic Styles from Formative Period Northern Peru, 1800-200 BC”. Doctoral Thesis, University of East Anglia, 2014.
<https://ueaeprints.uea.ac.uk/id/eprint/54452/>.

Reference: Park Huntington, Yumi . “Emblems of Cultural Identity in Early Andean Art: Engraved Head Motifs on Cupisnique Ceramics”. In *Ceramics of Ancient America: Multidisciplinary Approaches*, edited by Yumi Park Huntington, Dean E. Arnold, and Johanna Minich, 131-55. Gainesville, FL: University Press of Florida, 2018.
<https://doi.org/10.5744/florida/9780813056067.003.0005>.

Reference: Pozorski, Thomas. “The Early Horizon Site of Huaca De Los Reyes: Societal Implications”. *American Antiquity* 45, no. 1 (January 1980): 100-110.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/279663>.

Reference: Cordy-Collins, Alana. “Archaism or Tradition?: The Decapitation Theme in

Cupisnique and Moche Iconography". *Latin American Antiquity* 3, no. 3 (September 1992): 206–20. <https://doi.org/10.2307/971715>.

Reference: Shibata, Koichiro. "Cosmología Tripartita En Huaca Partida, Valle Bajo De Nepeña". *Indiana* 34, no. 1 (2017): 13–29. <https://doi.org/10.18441/ind.v34i1.13-29>.

Reference: Burger, Richard L.. *Chavin and the Origins of Andean Civilization*. Thames and Hudson, 1992.

Reference: Sghinolfi, Amedeo, Jean-François Millaire, Jeisen Navarro Vega, and Estuardo La Torre Calvera. "A Group of Geoglyphs in the Lower Carabamba Valley, Northern Peru". *Latin American Antiquity* 33, no. 3 (September 22, 2021): 632–40. <https://doi.org/10.1017/laq.2021.60>.

Reference: Franco Jordán, Régulo, and Feren Castillo Luján. "Hallazgo De Una Pintura Mural Temprana En La Huaca Tomabal, Valle De Virú, Perú". *Arqueología Y Sociedad* 37 (2022): 7–25. <https://doi.org/10.15381/arqueolsoc.2022n37.e23165>.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: Human figures were depicted in various positions/moments on pots. More specifically, possible shamans transforming into feline-like figures were usually depicted.

Reference: Park Huntington, Yumi . "Emblems of Cultural Identity in Early Andean Art: Engraved Head Motifs on Cupisnique Ceramics". In *Ceramics of Ancient America: Multidisciplinary Approaches*, edited by Yumi Park Huntington, Dean E. Arnold, and Johanna Minich, 131–55. Gainesville, FL: University Press of Florida, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.5744/florida/9780813056067.003.0005>.

Reference: Burtenshaw-Zumstein, Julia T.. "Cupisnique, Tembladera, Chongoyape, Chavín? A Typology of Ceramic Styles from Formative Period Northern Peru, 1800-200 BC". Doctoral Thesis, University of East Anglia, 2014. <https://ueaeprints.uea.ac.uk/id/eprint/54452/>.

Reference: Burger, Richard L.. *Chavin and the Origins of Andean Civilization*. Thames and Hudson, 1992.

Reference: Elera Arevalo, Carlos Gustavo. "El Complejo Cultural Cupisnique:

Antecedentes Y Desarrollo De Su Ideologia Religiosa". In El Mundo Ceremonial Andino, edited by Luis Millones and Yoshio Onuki, 37:229-57. Senri Ethnological Studies. Tokyo: National Museum of Ethnology, 1993. <https://doi.org/10.15021/00003040>.

↳ Other features of iconography:
– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:
– Field doesn't know

Are pilgrimages present:
– Field doesn't know

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– Field doesn't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:
– No

↳ Mummification:
– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Reference: Elera Arevalo, Carlos Gustavo. "The Puemape Site and the Cupisnique Culture: A Case Study on the Origins and Development of Complex Society in the Central Andes, Peru". Doctoral thesis, University of Calgary, 1998. <http://hdl.handle.net/1880/26224>.

Reference: Zoubek, Thomas A.. "The Initial Period Occupation of Huaca El Gallo/huaca La Gallina, Virú Valley, Peru and Its Implications for Guañape Phase Social Complexity". PhD Dissertation, Yale University, 1997.

Reference: Elera Arevalo, Carlos Gustavo, and José Pinilla Blenke. "Rites Funéraires À Puémape Pendant La Periode Formative". In *Le Pérou De L'origine Aux Incas*, Vol. 2. Les Dossiers D' Archeologie, 1992.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel. "Gramalote: Domestic Life, Economy and Ritual Practices of a Prehispanic Maritime Community". PhD Thesis, Yale University, 2015.

Reference: Nesbitt, Jason. "Excavations at Caballo Muerto: An Investigation into the Origins of the Cupisnique Culture". PhD dissertation, Yale University, 2012.

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

Notes: While there is high variability in the position of the bodies, this is the most common position.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel. "Gramalote: Domestic Life, Economy and Ritual Practices of a Prehispanic Maritime Community". PhD Thesis, Yale University, 2015.

Reference: Elera Arevalo, Carlos Gustavo. "The Puemape Site and the Cupisnique Culture: A Case Study on the Origins and Development of Complex Society in the Central Andes, Peru". Doctoral thesis, University of Calgary, 1998. <http://hdl.handle.net/1880/26224>.

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Even though there is no conclusive proof, possible evidence of cannibalism was found by Jason Nesbitt at the Caballo Muerto Complex in the Moche Valley. Human bones were found along with feasting remains.

Reference: Nesbitt, Jason. "Excavations at Caballo Muerto: An Investigation into the Origins of the Cupisnique Culture". PhD dissertation, Yale University, 2012.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: Secondary burials (with missing bones) have been reported at Gramalote in the Moche Valley. At Puemape in the Jequetepeque Valley some burials were disturbed during Prehispanic times and bones were removed/missing.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel. "Gramalote: Domestic Life, Economy and Ritual Practices of a Prehispanic Maritime Community". PhD Thesis, Yale University, 2015.

Reference: Elera Arevalo, Carlos Gustavo. "The Puemape Site and the Cupisnique Culture: A Case Study on the Origins and Development of Complex Society in the Central Andes, Peru". Doctoral thesis, University of Calgary, 1998. <http://hdl.handle.net/1880/26224>.

Reference: Pozorski, Shelia, and Thomas Pozorski. "An Early Subsistence Exchange System in the Moche Valley, Peru". *Journal of Field Archaeology* 6, no. 4 (1979): 413-32. <https://doi.org/10.1179/009346979791489023>.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Yes [specify]: Decaptations/amputations of bodies, presence of hematite on skulls (Puemape in the Jequetepeque Valley)

Notes: Decapitations and amputations (toes, arms, hands) were noted by Carlos Elera at Puemape (Middle Puemape burials).

Reference: Elera Arevalo, Carlos Gustavo. "The Puemape Site and the Cupisnique Culture: A Case Study on the Origins and Development of Complex Society in the Central Andes, Peru". Doctoral thesis, University of Calgary, 1998. <http://hdl.handle.net/1880/26224>.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: Based on data collected at burials excavated in the Huacapongo (Zoubek), Moche (Prieto) and Jequetepeque (Elera) valleys.

Reference: Burger, Richard L. *Chavin and the Origins of Andean Civilization*. Thames and Hudson, 1992.

Reference: Elera Arevalo, Carlos Gustavo. "The Puemape Site and the Cupisnique Culture: A Case Study on the Origins and Development of Complex Society in the Central Andes, Peru". Doctoral thesis, University of Calgary, 1998. <http://hdl.handle.net/1880/26224>.

Reference: Zoubek, Thomas A. "The Initial Period Occupation of Huaca El Gallo/huaca La Gallina, Virú Valley, Peru and Its Implications for Guañape Phase Social Complexity". PhD Dissertation, Yale University, 1997.

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: - stone, bone, and shell ornaments (pendants, necklaces, earspools) - pots - gourds - shells, fish bones and teeth perhaps connected to fishing activities - wooden and bone snuff tablets - wooden tools - red pigment (cinnabar) - Anthracite mirrors (Lambayeque and Moche valleys) Gabriel Prieto suggested that objects like anthracite mirrors, red pigment, and snuff tablets may have been buried with male shamans. An example is burial T223-1 from Gramalote (Moche Valley).

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel. "Gramalote: Domestic Life, Economy and Ritual Practices of a Prehispanic Maritime Community". PhD Thesis, Yale University, 2015.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel. "The Social Dynamics and Economic Interactions of the Households at Gramalote, a Small-scale Residential Settlement During the Second Millennium BC on the North Coast of Peru". *Latin American Antiquity* 29, no. 3 (September 2018): 532-51. <https://doi.org/10.1017/laq.2018.10>.

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: - Golden ornaments, also in the shape of jaguars and sea creatures (Lambayeque valley)

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– No

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– No

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: - large boulders on the body of the deceased - cotton textiles folded into small packets in the mouth cavities (Puemape)

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Formal cemeteries were identified by Rafael Larco Hoyle in several Northern Peruvian valleys; nevertheless, few information have been published about Larco's excavations. More information is available from the excavations conducted by Carlos Elera in the Lambayeque (Morro de Eten) and Jequetepeque Valley (Puemape). At Puemape, Cupisnique burials were located throughout the site. Elera highlights that areas that first had a residential function were later converted into cemeteries. Individuals were usually flexed and featured a variety of orientations. Children were buried in marginal areas. At Morro de Eten, several individuals were in an extended position, featured a North East orientation.

Reference: Kaulicke, Peter, and Lawrence S. Owens. "Death and the Dead in Formative Perú". In *Funerary Practices and Models in the Ancient Andes: The Return of the Living Dead*, edited by Peter Eeckhout, 12-23. Cambridge University Press, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107444928.003>.

Reference: Elera Arevalo, Carlos Gustavo. "The Puemape Site and the Cupisnique Culture: A Case Study on the Origins and Development of Complex Society in the Central Andes, Peru". Doctoral thesis, University of Calgary, 1998. <http://hdl.handle.net/1880/26224>.

Reference: Larco Hoyle, Rafael. *Los Cupisniques*, 1945.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: Almost half (45%) of the burials (adults, infants, males, females) found at Gramalote in

the Moche Valley were in residential contexts, including within houses (up to 6 individuals were buried in a single domestic building). Even though DNA analyses have not been conducted, it has been suggested that people buried in these residential units were related.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel. "The Social Dynamics and Economic Interactions of the Households at Gramalote, a Small-scale Residential Settlement During the Second Millennium BC on the North Coast of Peru". *Latin American Antiquity* 29, no. 3 (September 2018): 532-51. <https://doi.org/10.1017/laq.2018.10>.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel. "Gramalote: Domestic Life, Economy and Ritual Practices of a Prehispanic Maritime Community". PhD Thesis, Yale University, 2015.

Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Burials were identified nearby ceremonial structures at sites like Huaca El Gallo and Huaca La Gallina (Huacapongo Valley) or in ceremonial areas like at Gramalote (Moche Valley). In the latter case, a burial of a possible shaman (T223-1) was found in the central plaza of the residential sector, and several burials were found in the ceremonial sector of the site. At Morro de Eten (Lambayeque Valley), some burials may have had special connection with the sea: they were located near the Ocean and they were dug into hematite sands that turn red towards sunset (see Kaulicke 2015).

Reference: Zoubek, Thomas A.. "The Initial Period Occupation of Huaca El Gallo/huaca La Gallina, Virú Valley, Peru and Its Implications for Guañape Phase Social Complexity". PhD Dissertation, Yale University, 1997.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel. "The Social Dynamics and Economic Interactions of the Households at Gramalote, a Small-scale Residential Settlement During the Second Millennium BC on the North Coast of Peru". *Latin American Antiquity* 29, no. 3 (September 2018): 532-51. <https://doi.org/10.1017/laq.2018.10>.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel. "Gramalote: Domestic Life, Economy and Ritual Practices of a Prehispanic Maritime Community". PhD Thesis, Yale University, 2015.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel. "The Temple of the Fishermen: Early Ceremonial Architecture at Gramalote, a Residential Settlement of the Second Millennium B.C., North Coast of Peru". *Journal of Field Archaeology* 43, no. 3 (2018): 200-221. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00934690.2018.1441573>.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

A supreme high god is present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While it is not clear, the clay anthropomorphic heads found at Huaca de los Reyes in the Moche Valley were interpreted as a possible creator god.

Reference: Pozorski, Thomas. "The Early Horizon Site of Huaca De Los Reyes: Societal

Implications". *American Antiquity* 45, no. 1 (January 1980): 100-110.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/279663>.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
– Yes

Notes: Anthropomorphic figures (winged beings, decapitators, warriors) and animals (snakes, raptorial birds, jaguars, spiders) may have been considered supernatural beings. As mentioned in the General Variables - Architecture and Geography - Iconography section, anthropomorphic figures may have been culture heroes or mediators between worlds. The animals mentioned above may have been related to water and fertility, but may have also represented the celestial world (hanan pacha), our world (kay pacha), and the underworld (uku pacha).

Reference: Burger, Richard L. *Chavin and the Origins of Andean Civilization*. Thames and Hudson, 1992.

Reference: Pozorski, Thomas. "The Early Horizon Site of Huaca De Los Reyes: Societal Implications". *American Antiquity* 45, no. 1 (January 1980): 100-110.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/279663>.

Reference: Zoubek, Thomas A. "The Initial Period Occupation of Huaca El Gallo/huaca La Gallina, Virú Valley, Peru and Its Implications for Guañape Phase Social Complexity". PhD Dissertation, Yale University, 1997.

Reference: Shibata, Koichiro. "Cosmología Tripartita En Huaca Partida, Valle Bajo De Nepeña". *Indiana* 34, no. 1 (2017): 13-29. <https://doi.org/10.18441/ind.v34i1.13-29>.

Reference: Steele, Paul Richard, and Catherine Jean Allen. *Handbook of Inca Mythology*. Bloomsbury Publishing, 2004.

Reference: Cordy-Collins, Alana. "Archaism or Tradition?: The Decapitation Theme in Cupisnique and Moche Iconography". *Latin American Antiquity* 3, no. 3 (September 1992): 206-20.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/971715>.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - Yes
 - Notes: SPONDYLUS
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Field doesn't know

Is an eschatology present:

– Field doesn't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Two possible human sacrifices (Burial XCIX-C) were found at Puemape in the Jequetepeque Valley by Carlos Elera (1998: 122, 525). These two individuals were mutilated and were not carefully placed in the burial pit. At Huaca La Gallina (Huacapongo Valley), Thomas Zoubek posits that a female individual (20-25 years old) may have been sacrificed (dedicatory sacrifice) and interred in a circular structure that may have had a ritual function.

Reference: Elera Arevalo, Carlos Gustavo. "The Puemape Site and the Cupisnique Culture: A Case Study on the Origins and Development of Complex Society in the Central Andes, Peru". Doctoral thesis, University of Calgary, 1998. <http://hdl.handle.net/1880/26224>.

Reference: Zoubek, Thomas A.. "The Initial Period Occupation of Huaca El Gallo/huaca La Gallina, Virú Valley, Peru and Its Implications for Guañape Phase Social Complexity". PhD Dissertation, Yale University, 1997.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: The adherents to this cult likely participated in gatherings that took place in the plaza and temples that entailed ritual feasting (food remains like fish, tubers, camelid bones, and bowls were found in ritual contexts at the Caballo Muerto Complex in the Moche Valley). Evidence of possible feasting events (food preparation areas, broken pots, food remains) was also recorded at smaller sites like Gramalote in the Moche Valley. The ceremonial center at the fishing village of Gramalote likely hosted smaller rituals compared to large ceremonial centers like Caballo Muerto. These rituals (likely connected to the Ocean and its resources) may have involved only the head of each family living at Gramalote. This ceremonial center may have also been a place where decisions about fishing strategies were taken.

Reference: Nesbitt, Jason. "Excavations at Caballo Muerto: An Investigation into the Origins of the Cupisnique Culture". PhD dissertation, Yale University, 2012.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel. "The Temple of the Fishermen: Early Ceremonial Architecture at Gramalote, a Residential Settlement of the Second Millennium B.C., North Coast of Peru". *Journal of Field Archaeology* 43, no. 3 (2018): 200-221. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00934690.2018.1441573>.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Evidence (ritual caches with anthracite mirrors, shells, fish bones and teeth) found in the domestic sector of Gramalote in the Moche Valley suggests that domestic rituals were also carried out.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned above, the adherents to this cult likely participated in gatherings. These meetings may have been a way for incipient elites to mobilize labor and renovate ceremonial centers (participation in rituals in exchange for labor).

Reference: Nesbitt, Jason. "Excavations at Caballo Muerto: An Investigation into the Origins of the Cupisnique Culture". PhD dissertation, Yale University, 2012.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:
– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:
– Yes

Notes: Bone and wooden snuff tablets and tubes found at ceremonial centers suggest that psychoactive substances were used by shamans/religious leaders during rituals.

Reference: Burger, Richard L.. *Chavin and the Origins of Andean Civilization*. Thames and Hudson, 1992.

Reference: Elera Arevalo, Carlos Gustavo. "The Puemape Site and the Cupisnique Culture: A Case Study on the Origins and Development of Complex Society in the Central Andes, Peru". Doctoral thesis, University of Calgary, 1998. <http://hdl.handle.net/1880/26224>.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Recent research by Jason Nesbitt at Caballo Muerto in the Moche Valley suggests that Cupisnique people were likely organized in small communities where power was ephemeral and based on ritual knowledge. Each mound at the ceremonial centers may have thus been produced and renovated by a specific community/kin group.

Reference: Nesbitt, Jason. "Excavations at Caballo Muerto: An Investigation into the Origins of the Cupisnique Culture". PhD dissertation, Yale University, 2012.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: As highlighted by research conducted in Northern Peru (especially by Brian Billman and Thomas Zoubek), during the Initial Period and the Early Horizon there was likely an expansion of the previous

(Late Preceramic Period) incipient irrigation networks. Middle valleys and valley necks were prime locations for canal intakes and several ceremonial centers were built in such areas. These irrigation networks were likely not very complex and managed by small communities (which may have also cooperated to clean the main canal intake) rather than by a centralized authority/state. However, religious leaders/elites may have played a role in overseeing the construction and maintenance of water canals.

Reference: Zoubek, Thomas A.. "The Initial Period Occupation of Huaca El Gallo/huaca La Gallina, Virú Valley, Peru and Its Implications for Guañape Phase Social Complexity". PhD Dissertation, Yale University, 1997.

Reference: Billman, Brian R.. "Irrigation and the Origins of the Southern Moche State on the North Coast of Peru". *Latin American Antiquity* 13, no. 4 (December 2002): 371-400. <https://doi.org/10.2307/972222>.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Field doesn't know

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Food was likely produced/gathered by individual families/small communities

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: Gathering (seaweed, seashells) Hunting (deer) Fishing (several fish species from the Pacific Ocean) Pastoralism (domesticated camelids, likely llamas) Agriculture (bean, maize, manioc, potato, squash, chili peppers, lucuma, avocado)

Reference: Zoubek, Thomas A.. "The Initial Period Occupation of Huaca El Gallo/huaca La Gallina, Virú Valley, Peru and Its Implications for Guañape Phase Social Complexity". PhD Dissertation, Yale University, 1997.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel. "Gramalote: Domestic Life, Economy and Ritual Practices of a Prehispanic Maritime Community". PhD Thesis, Yale University, 2015.

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Reference: Nesbitt, Jason. "Excavations at Caballo Muerto: An Investigation into the Origins of the Cupisnique Culture". PhD dissertation, Yale University, 2012.

Reference: Pozorski, Shelia. "Prehistoric Diet and Subsistence of the Moche Valley, Peru". *World Archaeology* 11, no. 2 (1979): 163–84. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00438243.1979.9979759>.

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Funérais À Puémape Pendant La Periode Formative”. In *Le Pérou De L'origine Aux Incas*, Vol. 2. Les Dossiers D' Archeologie, 1992.

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